

USING ACTIVE METHODS IN FINE ARTS LESSONS

Smaylova Gulmari Yuldashevna

Regional center of Public education of Karakalpakstan Republic

Summary: *The state speaks of the use of active teaching methods in teaching fine arts, the development of the student's ability to actively learn, conducting such classes in the art of stimulation.*

Keywords: *visual arts, student, active teaching methods, lessons, heuristic conversation.*

Rezyume: *Maqolada tasviriy san'at darslarida o'qitishning faol usullaridan foydalanish, ta'lim oluvchilarda faol o'rganish qobiliyati, ya'ni ta'lim oluvchilarning ijod qilish va o'rganishga qiziqishini yuzaga chiqaruvchi faoliyat haqida yozilgan*

Kalit so'zlar: *Tasviriy san'at, o'quvchi, o'qitishning faol usullari, dars, evristik suhbat.*

Резюме: *В статье говорится о применении активных методов обучения в преподавании изобразительного искусства, о развитии у учащихся способности активно учиться, то есть проведении таких занятий, которые стимулируют интерес учащихся к творчеству и обучению.*

Ключевые слова: *изобразительное искусство, студент, активные методы обучения, уроки, эвристическая беседа.*

In our country, there are many opportunities for a radical reform of the education system, the widespread use of communication tools, as well as the development of the intellectual and creative potential of young people. It is very important to acquaint students with the values of our country, its rich culture, improve their skills, enrich them, form aesthetic concepts, form requirements for gaining knowledge about culture and art.

Without a deep knowledge of the centuries-old values, the vast, rich and cultural heritage of our people, it is impossible to understand national identity, a sense of national pride. The cultural wealth they create serves as an important tool in educating young people. Through the writings of great thinkers, students gain a broad understanding of the rules of good morality, happiness, honesty, purity, kindness, and respect for parents. The teacher's contribution to the upbringing of the younger generation is invaluable.

In particular, in the implementation of the educational process, a specific goal is set, laws are adopted, programs and activities are developed, plans are established that are implemented at the current level of demand. So, design before education is a project, construction, pedagogical technology of a certain pedagogical system. From this point of view, “personality formation” is also a project of a certain pedagogical system.

There is a goal, content, methods, forms and means of upbringing a harmoniously developed person, which is also a unique technology. Today, the state pays special attention to educating the younger generation in educational institutions, as well as creating the necessary conditions for all teachers to work on themselves, conducting research and organizing the educational process at the level of modern requirements on a scientific basis. Increasing the level of knowledge, experience and level of teachers, a condition for awareness of innovations in their field is their attitude to independent work.

Educational innovations are forms, methods and technologies that can be used to solve a problem in the field of education or the educational process on the basis of a new approach and guarantee a more effective result than before. [1;10]

One of the most important problems in teaching fine arts today is the establishment of targeted education. In the field of visual arts, the goal is to accelerate the development of students' intellectual abilities through the acquisition of historical knowledge, concepts and ideas about the visual arts, their interpretation, and the formation of skills and competencies. Intellectual potential requires joint actions of teacher and student.

That is, they have a choice of which technology to use to achieve the goal, because the main goal of both parties is to achieve a clear result, depending on the level of knowledge of the students, the nature of the group, the technology used, for example: a film, handouts, drawings and posters, various publications, information technology will be needed, it depends on the teacher and the student.

The teacher must design the educational process in advance, in which the teacher must take into account the specifics, location and conditions of the subject, and, most importantly, the abilities and needs of the student, as well as the ability to organize joint activities so that the desired guaranteed result can be achieved. Achieving such a result requires the use of innovative and information technologies in the educational process in practice. [1;64]

Interactive learning, interactive methods of regular communication it is a system of methods based on the collaborative and active learning of students it is a system and methods of collaborative learning. In other words, interactive teaching methods -

cognitive and communication activities it is a special form of organization in which students know are involved in the process, know and think they will be able to understand and think. [2;11]

They are very different. These include new interactive teaching methods and methods, as well as modern technologies currently used in the educational process. At the same time, it should be noted that with the widespread use of the aforementioned modern methods or technological trainings, which help to increase the effectiveness of learning, students develop logical, intellectual, creative, critical and independent thinking.

In particular, it helps students develop their skills, become competitive, mature professionals and develop the professional qualities required by a specialist. Active learning is a systemic pedagogical process that ensures conscious and active participation, independence and creativity of teachers and students in the educational process. The methods of cognition and action acquired in an active learning environment are ideally structured in content, logically complete and suitable for use in various work situations.

The following teaching methods are mainly used:

- discussion - discussion; participation in thinking; reinforcement on the board;
- introduction of various educational and professional games, etc.

The ability to actively learn from students studying the visual arts, that is, an active approach that stimulates students' interest in research (creativity) and learning (aspiration), can be the main didactic basis for activating teaching methods.

Active learning methods are methods that encourage students to think and practice as they learn the material. Active learning involves the use of a method that is focused primarily on the teacher's presentation of ready-made knowledge, and not on memorizing and retrieving them by students, but on the students' independent acquisition of knowledge and skills in the process of active perception and practice.

The characteristics of active teaching methods are to encourage students to actively perceive and practice, without which it is impossible to move forward in the acquisition of knowledge. The educational process was preceded by the emergence and development of active teaching methods. It is characterized not only by the transfer of knowledge to students, but also by new tasks, including cognitive interests and abilities, creative thinking, as well as the formation and development of skills of independent mental work.

The emergence of new tasks is based on the rapid development of information. Active teaching methods are used at different stages of the educational process: the initial acquisition of knowledge, consolidation and improvement of knowledge, the formation of skills.

When choosing a teaching methodology, first of all, it is important to analyze the content of the educational material and the creative thinking of students using active methods, their cognitive abilities, life experience, the ability to adapt to real activities.

Informative learning methods include the ways in which students receive instructional information in a finished form or in which the teacher can narrate: lecture, storytelling, explanation, conversation, independent work with a book. A distinctive feature of problem-based teaching methods is the addition of questions for students to which they need to find independent answers, create new knowledge for themselves, “discover” and formulate theoretical conclusions.

Education - for purposeful personal improvement is an organized pedagogical process that allows you to systematically and systematically influence the teacher. [3;63]

These include: problem report, heuristic dialogue, research report, search lab, research method. The essence of active skills-building methods is to get students to complete tasks that they can take on in the solution process. The science of fine arts education provides the younger generation with a wide range of opportunities for the formation and development of aesthetic taste, artistic thinking, intellectual potential and, most importantly, a general outlook.

Thus, the introduction of promising innovative approaches based on historical experience, analysis of modern situations over a certain period of time, will ensure the development of the industry, the correspondence of art education to the educational needs of society.

So, you need to understand that the creative thinking of students, the new formation of artistic thinking allows you to achieve positive results only with the help of modern approaches. The educational task of visual arts is to convey the rich cultural, artistic and aesthetic heritage created by humanity to future generations, to satisfy the needs of people, to control their emotions, to change the world based on the laws of beauty. Our experienced teachers will achieve the desired results with a positive approach.

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